

Effect of intercropping on growth and yield of some Leguminous and Cereal forage crops in El Kadaru Area

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ABSTRACT

Intercropping is not a common practice in forage production in Sudan, in spite of its importance; farmers don't know the potentiality of this type of cultivation and more experiments needed to adopt this type of cropping system and it is an example of biological interaction. A field experiment was conducted under irrigation for two consecutive seasons during 2013/2014 and 2015/2016 in the demonstration farm, college of Animal production, University of Bahri, Sudan to study the effect of intercropping of two leguminous forage crops (clitoria and phillipesara) cultivated with one non leguminous crop (Sorghum). Randomized complete block design (RCBD) was used. Yield of sole crops produced more forage, but the total yield (Over yielding) of the intercropped plants as revealed by land equivalent ratio was higher compared with the individual crops. Clitoria growth parameters (plant height, number of leaves and stem diameter) were not significantly affected by intercropping, but there was significant difference in plant population in the two seasons. Intercropping did not significantly affect growth parameters during the two seasons of Phillipesa except plant population and the first reading of plant height. Sorghum showed significant differences in plant population and some readings during the two seasons (the fourth reading of plant height in the first season, the first reading of number of leaves in first season, the fourth reading of stem diameter in the first season and the first reading of stem diameter in the second season).

KEYWORDS

Cropping System, Sole Crop, Land Equivalent Ratio (LER), Biological Interaction

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Applying the concept of sustainability in forage production is the current issue of many forage researchers and producers. Livestock depend mainly on natural pastures and crop residues which are often limiting in quantity and nutritional quality (Andrea and Pablo, 1999). The limiting feed supply to animals results in weight loss and ill-health (Birteeb *et al.*, 2011). Practicing intercropping as a method of crop cultivation do not harm the environment, provide fair treatment to workers, support and sustain local communities. It is the coming back to the rule of the nature, diversity and heterogeneity of the plants. Intercropping considers

the principles of agroecology and sustainability, which uses there renewable resources of energy instead of non-renewable sources. It is the production system of food for human, forage for animals and green manure for soil fertilization. Intercropping is a ways to increase diversity in an agricultural ecosystem (Mousavi and Eskandari, 2011). Intercropping systems can cause more effective use of resources by providing symbiotic nitrogen from legumes or making available inorganic phosphorus fixed in soil (Aminifar and Ghanbari, 2014). Sudan endowed with huge livestock wealth.

It has more than 106 million heads of animals (The Sudan Today, 2019), concentrated mainly on the western and the southern states of the country. These areas are suffering from unequal distribution of rainfall and drought is the common feature. Livestock depends on grazing natural range and resulted in their deterioration of natural pastures which are not satisfying the required quantity and quality for animal production (Khair, 1999). The actual amount of forage available for animal about 108 million ton, but the amount needed about 122 million tons according to the report of Range management (2015). Livestock production depends mainly on the development of forage crop production, due to the shortage of forage materials, irrigated forage crops using intercropping can bridge the gap caused by the reduction in range land production. Animals are doing well in sustainable forage production; they are useful in converting vast renewable resources from rangeland, pasture, and crop residues or other by-products into food edible for humans. The present study was initiated to study the effect of intercropping on growth and yield of clitoria, pillipesara and sorghum. Also to evaluate the performance of these leguminous and grass forage crops under the local condition.

Materials and Methods

The field experiment was conducted for two seasons during 2013/2014 and 2015/2016 in the demonstration farm of the college of animal production at El Kadaru area. The land preparation operations were done using disk plough, harrowing, leveling, and ridging 70 cm apart. The size of the plot was 4 x 5 m with 5 ridges. The experiment was ranged in randomized complete block design with four replication and 6th treatments which were as follow: clitoria, pillipesara, sorghum, clitoria: sorghum, pillipesara: sorghum and clitoria: sorghum: pillipesara. Seed rate for sorghum, clitoria and pillipesara, seeding rates applied were, 20, 15, 10 kg/feddans, respectively. In case of mixture, the seed rate was half or third of that of the sole crop. Seeds of legumes were drilled on the shoulders of the ridges, alternated with Sorghum seeds, row intercropping (1:1). The experiment was irrigated immediately after planting to avoid death of bacteria (*Rhizobium*) and weekly thereafter. Five tagged plants for each crop in the plot was taken randomly from the middle rows to measure growth

parameters (plant population, stem diameter, plant height, number of leaves, leaf area, yield and land equivalent ratio).

Results and Discussion

Cereal-legumes intercropping systems, comparatively taller cereals render a shading effect that reduced the physiological growth of leguminous intercrops, which called for the need to optimize the spatial arrangement and canopy structure of component crops.

Clitoria

No significant difference was recorded throughout the two seasons in clitoria, but there was slight increase in plant height when clitoria intercropped with sorghum and pillipesara. The slight increase in plant height is an indication of increase plant cover and the obvious significant ability of clitoria to cover the area could be due to the higher number of plants per unit area as reported by (Abuswar and Omer, 2011). Number of leaves were significantly differences in reading two, three and fourth leaves per plant in the first season. Sole crops carried more leaves than the intercropped plants. The high plant population may justify the decrease in number of leaves that is because the increase in branches and stems of plants due to reduced seed rate (Khairi, 1980).

Clitoria plant population was significantly affected by intercropping throughout the two seasons. The sole crops of clitoria were higher in number of plant per squire mater followed by C:S and then C:S:P combination this could be due to the smallest size of the clitoria seeds. The overall yield was higher as indicated by land equivalent ratio this is may referred to the effect of intercropping in increasing the quality and yield of the product (Mousavi and Eskandari, 2011). More forage was significantly obtained from plots grown by sole crops followed by C:S and C:S:P combinations.

Phillipesara

Plant height was not significantly affected by intercropping in all readings during the two seasons except reading one in the first season, in which P: S treatment scored the highest plants, similar result was reported by (Prajapati and Kewalanand, 2017) under different intercropping systems.

Table 1. Effect of intercropping on plant height (cm) of Clitoria

Treatment	Season 1				Season 2			
	Reading 1	Reading 2	Reading 3	Reading 4	Reading 1	Reading 2	Reading 3	Reading 4
C	10.57 B	14.98A	21.89A	23.66A	20.28A	39.45A	26.49A	33.85A
C:S	13.40A	18.14A	22.59A	24.32A	23.68A	13.15A	16.50A	18.20A
C:S:P	12.54A	16.65A	70.48A	21.08A	23.67A	13.11A	17.70A	19.60A
SE+	0.4234	1.73	30.13	2.9931	67.40	186.47	6.62	7.24
CV	6.96	20.89	26	26.00	7.60	305.94	65.42	60.83

Means with the same letter (s) within each column are not significantly different at 0.05 level using Duncan's Multiple Range Test. Legend: C = clitoria P = phillipesear , S = sorghum.

Table 2. Effect of intercropping on number of leaves of Clitoria

Treatment	Season 1				Season 2			
	Reading 1	Reading 2	Reading 3	Reading 4	Reading 1	Reading 2	Reading 3	Reading 4
C	6.400 A	14.10A	21.40A	22.50A	19.30A	15.40A	10.70A	17.200
C:S	6.450 A	12.60AB	13.15B	13.35B	21.95A	6.88A	8.30A	16.950
C:S:P	4.850 A	9.750 B	11.20B	11.40B	10.56A	7.70A	8.45A	19.200
SE+	0.523	1.03	1.52	1.99	7.78	5.097	2.075	11.23
CV	17.71	16.99	25.22	25.22	84.27	102.04	45.35	126.33

Means with the same letter (s) within each column are not significantly different at 0.05 level using Duncan's Multiple Range Test. Legend: C = clitoria P = phillipesear , S = sorghum

Table 3. Effect of intercropping on stem diameter of Clitoria

Treatment	Season 1				Season 2			
	Reading 1	Reading 2	Reading 3	Reading 4	Reading 1	Reading 2	Reading 3	Reading 4
C	0.135A	0.21A	0.27A	0.32A		0.22A	0.30A	0.28A
C:S	0.18A	0.21A	0.27A	0.28A	0.27A	0.19A	0.25A	0.28A
C:S:P	0.15A	0.23A	0.24A	0.26A	0.28A	0.20A	0.25A	0.32A
SE+	0.0316	0.0331	0.032	0.0233	0.220	0.038	0.033	0.058
CV	41.19	30.81	25.08	16.33	0.0419	33.56	25.13	40.18

Means with the same letter (s) within each column are not significantly different at 0.05 level using Duncan's Multiple Range Test. Legend: C = clitoria P = phillipesear , S = sorghum

Table 4. Effect of intercropping on plant population of clitoria (plants/m²)

Treatment	Season 1				Season 2			
	Reading 1	Reading 2	Reading 3	Reading 4	Reading 1	Reading 2	Reading 3	Reading 4
C	44.75A	41.75A	40.75A	40.80A	11.00A	7.25AB	25.75A	12.25A
C:S	19.75A	28.25AB	28.25AB	28.25AB	6.250B	4.500B	16.25B	12.00A
C:S:P	30.00A	13.25B	13.25B	13.25B	17.75AB	7.500A	19.00B	7.000B
SE+	9.71	4.73	4.73	4.72	2.52	0.812	1.15	0.845
CV	61.66	34.06	34.05	34.04	43.35	25.32	11.27	16.24

Means with the same letter (s) within each column are not significantly different at 0.05 level using Duncan's Multiple Range Test. Legend: C = clitoria P = phillipesear , S = sorghum

Table 5. Effect of intercropping, phosphorus and inoculation on fresh and dry yield (t/ha) of clitoria

Treatment	Season 1		Season 2	
	Fresh wt	Dry wt	Fresh wt	Dry wt
C	865.00A	596.94A	285.00A	88.290A
C:S	450.00B	313.05B	200.00AB	61.960AB
C:S:P	160.00C	110.41C	140.00 B	43.370B
SE+	69.702	48.216	40.79	12.64
CV	28.35	28.35	39.16	39.16

Means with the same letter (s) within each column are not significantly different at 0.05 level using Duncan's Multiple Range Test. Legend: C = clitoria P = phillipesear , S = sorghum

Table 6. Effect of intercropping on plant height (cm) of Phillipesar

Treatment	Season 1				Season 2			
	Reading 1	Reading 2	Reading 3	Reading 4	Reading 1	Reading 2	Reading 3	Reading 4
P	12.9A	13.7A	36.5A	37.5A	24.3A	19.8A	12.7A	16.9A
P:S	9.3AB	11.2A	14.6A	14.6A	20.4A	8.23A	13.0A	14.4A
P:S:C	6.28B	8.91A	11.7A	11.7A	34.2A	19.2A	13.2A	11.9A
SE+	1.74	2.67	9.76	9.66	59.28	4.902	3.253	4.478
CV%	37.15	47.37	93.17	93.27	7.800	62.21	50.24	62.11

Means with the same letter (s) within each column are not significantly different at 0.05 level using Duncan's Multiple Range Test.
Legend: C = clitoria P = phillipesear , S = sorghum

Table 7. Effect of intercropping on plant leave number of Phillipesar

Treatment	Season 1				Season 2			
	Reading 1	Reading 2	Reading 3	Reading 4	Reading 1	Reading 2	Reading 3	Reading 4
P	5.00A	6.05A	8.15A	10.85	12.3A	10.0A	9.50A	8.85A
P:S	4.20A	5.08A	5.13A	4.967	12.0A	6.35A	7.95A	8.68A
P:S:C	3.23A	5.23A	6.30A	6.850	9.30A	7.95A	6.40A	8.50A
SE+	1.02	0.897	1.57	2.03	3.337	3.123	1.297	57.76
CV	49.41	32.90	48.18	53.85	58.67	71.11	32.63	2.506

Means with the same letter (s) within each column are not significantly different at 0.05 level using Duncan's Multiple Range Test.
Legend: C = clitoria P = phillipesear , S = sorghum

Table 8. Effect of intercropping on stem diameter of Phillipesar

Treatment	Season 1				Season 2			
	Reading 1	Reading 2	Reading 3	Reading 4	Reading 1	Reading 2	Reading 3	Reading 4
P	0.160A	0.220A	0.255A	0.325A	0.370A	0.590A	0.325A	0.410A
P:S	0.369A	0.200A	0.228A	0.280A	0.280A	0.263A	0.293A	0.322A
P:S:C	0.115A	0.243A	0.220A	0.205A	0.300A	0.235A	0.260A	8.893A
SE+	6.66	0.0517	0.0422	0.0532	0.087	0.177	0.068	4.991
CV	277.69	46.69	36.02	39.41	54.78	97.67	47.07	311.14

Means with the same letter (s) within each column are not significantly different at 0.05 level using Duncan's Multiple Range Test.
Legend: C = clitoria P = phillipesear , S = sorghum

Table 9. Effect of intercropping on plant population of Phillipesar

Treatment	Season 1				Season 2			
	Reading 1	Reading 2	Reading 3	Reading 4	Reading 1	Reading 2	Reading 3	Reading 4
P	21.8A	21.0A	21.0A	21.0A	36.0A	29.0A	9.25A	37.5A
P:S	34.3A	26.0A	26.0A	26.0A	11.25B	21.3B	8.88A	20.8B
P:S:C	26.0A	14.0A	14.0A	14.0A	29.8A	21.5B	8.50A	4.00C
SE+	10.17	10.35	10.35	10.35	2.859	1.850	0.427	0.777
CV	74.35	101.82	101.82	101.82	22.28	15.47	9.62	7.49

Means with the same letter (s) within each column are not significantly different at 0.05 level using Duncan's Multiple Range Test.
Legend: C = clitoria P = phillipesear , S = sorghum

Table 10. Effect of intercropping, phosphorus and inoculation on fresh and dry yield (t/ha) of Phillipesar

Treatment	Season 1		Season 2	
	Fresh wt	Dry wt	Fresh wt	Dry wt
P	380.00 A	354.48	585.00 A	231.37A
P:S	266.67 A	162.98	170.00 B	67.23B
P:S:C	120.00 A	73.34	310.0AB	122.6AB
SE+	150.92	69.69	103.96	41.117
CV	118.11	70.77	58.57	59.57

Means with the same letter (s) within each column are not significantly different at 0.05 level using Duncan's Multiple Range Test.
Legend: C = clitoria P = phillipesear , S = sorghum

Table 11. Effect of intercropping on plant height (cm) of Sorghum

Treatment	Season 1				Season 2			
	Reading 1	Reading 2	Reading 3	Reading 4	Reading 1	Reading 2	Reading 3	Reading 4
S	41.48A	51.86A	56.31A	50.88B	88.20A	73.55A	51.60A	61.55A
S:P	46.04A	61.31A	69.95A	71.10A	84.70A	46.80A	57.65A	41.18A
S:C	51.58A	61.88A	70.13A	67.58AB	73.08A	57.15A	59.20A	47.35A
S:C:P	40.65A	63.40A	63.10A	62.13AB	83.20A	76.58A	42.70A	54.85A
SE+	5.32	6.80	5.78	6.27	9.72	11.32	11.78	12.032
CV	23.66	22.81	17.81	19.91	23.63	35.63	44.64	46.98

Means with the same letter (s) within each column are not significantly different at 0.05 level using Duncan's Multiple Range Test.
Legend: C = clitoria P = phillipesara , S = sorghum

Table 12. Effect of intercropping on leave number of Sorghum

Treatment	Season 1				Season 2			
	Reading 1	Reading 2	Reading 3	Reading 4	Reading 1	Reading 2	Reading 3	Reading 4
S	6.500B	6.400A	7.000A	5.150A	7.000A	7.700AB	8.475A	10.100A
S:P	5.950B	7.525A	7.000A	6.950A	8.800A	6.750AB	7.950A	9.100 A
S:C	8.550A	7.500A	7.825A	6.600A	8.450A	5.900B	9.550A	11.200A
S:C:P	6.250B	8.250A	7.760A	6.650A	7.550A	8.350A	9.250A	10.900A
SE+	0.339	0.779	0.477	0.607	0.800	0.717	1.593	1.854
CV	9.96	21.0	12.89	19.15	20.02	20.00	36.17	35.91

Means with the same letter (s) within each column are not significantly different at 0.05 level using Duncan's Multiple Range Test.
Legend: C = clitoria P = phillipesara , S = sorghum

Table 13. Effect of intercropping on stem diameter (cm) of Sorghum

Treatment	Season 1				Season 2			
	Reading 1	Reading 2	Reading 3	Reading 4	Reading 1	Reading 2	Reading 3	Reading 4
S	0.440A	0.940A	0.845A	0.820B	0.655B	1.160A	1.005A	1.490A
S:P	0.455A	0.830A	1.230A	1.220AB	1.620A	0.905A	0.900A	1.075A
S:C	0.600A	1.102A	1.045A	1.330A	1.250A	0.740A	1.430A	1.190A
S:C:P	0.490A	1.170A	1.105A	0.411AB	1.360A	1.220A	1.165A	1.400A
SE+	0.095	0.207	0.206	0.139	0.127	48.59	0.392	0.383
CV	38.58	41.01	38.98	24.43	20.94	0.245	69.70	59.36

Means with the same letter (s) within each column are not significantly different at 0.05 level using Duncan's Multiple Range Test.
Legend: C = clitoria P = phillipesara , S = sorghum

Table 14. Effect of intercropping on plant population of Sorghum

Treatment	Season 1				Season 2			
	Reading 1	Reading 2	Reading 3	Reading 4	Reading 1	Reading 2	Reading 3	Reading 4
S	43.00A	34.25A	38.63A	38.75A	42.75A	33.00AB	63.75A	26.50A
S:P	30.25AB	28.75A	29.50A	30.50AB	21.25C	33.50AB	72.75A	6.00C
S:C	19.00B	22.25A	25.63B	22.75B	28.75B	42.75A	11.00B	8.00C
S:C:P	28.75AB	28.75A	29.65A	29.05AB	16.75D	17.00B	8.75B	11.50B
SE+	6.71	6.33	13.00	16.00	1.40	5.22	3.003	0.96
CV	44.37	44.39	50.25	48.65	10.21	33.10	15.37	14.84

Means with the same letter (s) within each column are not significantly different at 0.05 level using Duncan's Multiple Range Test.
Legend: C = clitoria P = phillipesara , S = sorghum

No significant difference was observed during the two seasons in number of leaves. Plant population was high in sole crop plots and significantly in the majority of the readings in the two seasons. Although there were increase in stem diameters of sole crops but no significant effect was recorded. Sole crops were significantly scored high

yield in the second season, but first season yield was not significant, these results were confirm with that of (Shyam *et al.*, 2014). Who showed that total productivity of the systems in terms of dry 'pachang' equivalent yield and gross returns were twice higher and B:C ratio was thrice higher in sole cropping of phillipesara than intercropping with sweet sorghum.

Table 15. Effect of intercropping, phosphorus and inoculation on fresh and dry yield (t/ha) of Sorghum

Treatment	Season 1		Season 2	
	Fresh wt	Dry wt	Fresh wt	Dry wt
S	4300.0 A	28873 A	1285.0 A	414.98 A
S:P	3285.0 A	1334 A	1005.0 A	404.90 A
S:C	2055.0 A	835 A	1570.0 A	632.56 A
S:C:P	1915.0 A	778 A	1205.0 A	485.50 A
SE+	788.28	13444	241.57	34.84
CV	54.58	338.02	38.16	34.84

Means with the same letter (s) within each column are not significantly different at 0.05 level using Duncan's Multiple Range Test.

Legend: C = clitoria P = phillipesara , S = sorghum

Table 16. Effect of intercropping, phosphorus and inoculation on land Equivalent Ratio

Treatments	First Season	Second Season
C:S	1	1.9
S:C:P	1	1.96
S:P	1.46	1.96
C	1	1
P	1	1
S	1	1

Sorghum

In general, no significant difference was observed during the two seasons in plant height except reading number 4 in the first season in which sole crops scored highest plants. Similar results were obtained with sorghum and maize intercropped with cowpea or common beans by (Farist *et al.*, 1983). Number of leaves per plant was not significant except in the first reading of the first season and third reading of the second season. Approximately number of sole plants per plots (sorghum plant population) was significantly higher followed by S:P combination.

In most readings sole crops were thicker, but without significant difference except reading 4 in the first season and reading one in the second season. Fresh and dry yield were not significantly affected by intercropping but sole plots gave more yield. These results were agree with that of (Sani *et al.*, 2011) who reported that cereal-sorghum row intercropping system (1:1 row ratio) was effective in increasing water use efficiency because it produced more biomass per unit area by using the same quantity of water as compared to their sole cultivation.

Land Equivalent Ratio

In general intercropped plants gave more yields (more than one) and this could be due to higher growth rate, reduction of weeds, reducing the pest and diseases and more effective use of resources (Watiki, *et al.*, 1993). An intercropping trial of sorghum and cowpea under different row proportions showed that a 2:1 row proportion gave a better land equivalent ratio (LER) as compared to other planting patterns (Oseni, 2010).

Conclusion

The intercropping application was showed increase in plant growth parameters without significant differences between the three plants (Clitoria, Phillipesaara and Sorghum). The sole crops of the three plants obtained the highest rates of plant growth parameters and yield compared to intercropping application without significant differences during the two seasons.

References

- Aminifar, J. and Ghanbari, A. (2014) Biological facilitative interactions and their roles on maximize growth and productivity of crops in intercropping systems, *Scientia Agriculturae*, **2**(2): 90-95.
- Andrea, M. M. and Pablo, E. C. (1999) A tropical forage solution to poor quality ruminant diets: A review of *Lablab purpureus*, *Livestock Research for Rural Development*, **11**: 2. retrieved July 8, 2011 July 8, 2011, <http://www.lrrd.org/lrrd11/2/colu112.htm>.
- Birteeb, P. T., W., Addah, Naandam Jakper and A., Addo-Kwafo (2011) Effects of intercropping cereal-legume on biomass and grain yield in the Savannah Zone, *Livestock Research for Rural Development*.
- Eskandari, H. (2012) Intercropping of maize (*Zea mays*) with cowpea (*Vigna sinensis*) and mungbean (*Vigna radiata*), Effect of complementarity of intercrop components on resource consumption, dry matter production and legume forage production, *Journal of Basic and Applied Scientific Research*, **2**: 355-360.
- Farist, M. A., Burity, H. A. Dosreis, O. V. and Mafra, R. C. (1983) Intercropping of sorghum or maize with cow peas or common beans under two fertility regimes in *Northeastern Brazil Expl. Agric.* **19**: 251-261.
- Khair, M. A. (1998) The range lands and cereal forage resources which utilization in animal nutrition, A paper submitted to rangeland section conference in Sudan.
- Khair, M. A. M. (1999) Principles of forage production in Sudan, 1st. ed. Wad Medani, Sudan (in Arabic).
- Mousavi, S., R. and Eskandari, H. (2011) A general overview of intercropping and its advantages in Sustainable Agriculture, *J. Appl. Environ. Bio. Sci.* **111**: 482-486.
- Eskandari, H. (2012b) Intercropping of maize (*Zea mays*) with cowpea (*Vigna sinensis*) and mungbean (*Vigna radiata*): effect of complementarity of intercrop components on resource consumption, dry matter production and legumes forage quality, *Journal of Basic and Applied Scientific Research*, **2**: 355-360.
- Oseni, T. O. and Aliyu, I. G. (2010) Effect of row arrangements on sorghum-cowpea intercrops in the semi-arid savannah of Nigeria, *International Journal of Agriculture Biology*, **12**: 137-140.
- Prajapati, B. and Kewalanand (2017) Production potential of fodder based intercropping systems, *International Journal of Chemical Studies*, **5**(6): 834-838.
- Sani, B. M., Danmowa, N. M., Sani, Y. A. and Jaliya, M. M. (2011) Growth, yield and water use efficiency of maize-sorghum intercrop at Samaru, Northern Guinea Savannah, Nigeria, *Nigerian Journal of Basic and Applied Sciences*, **19**: 253-259.
- Shyam, S., K., Ramesh, C. and Anchal, D. (2014) Effect of integrated nutrient sources on fodder yield and quality of sweet sorghum [*Sorghum bicolor* (L.) moench.] and phillipesara (*Phaseolus trilobus*) inter cropping system, *Ann. Agric. Res.*, New series, **35**(2): 193-199.
- The Sudan Today (2019) Dry matter production and legumes forage quality, <https://alsudanalyoum.com/?p=202685>.
- Watiki, J., S., Mfukai, J. A. B. and B. A., Keating (1993) Radiation interception and growth of maize/cowpea intercrop as an affected by maize plant-density and cow pea cultivar, *Field Crop Research*, **35**: 123-133.